

The Influences of Leadership, Work Discipline, and Communication on Employees Performance

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Abstract:- This research aims to analyze the effect and find the most dominant influence on employee performance among independent variables: leadership, work discipline, and communication that will be made a priority of company improvement. This research used a survey method with quantitative analysis. The sampling technique used is probability sampling using stratified random sampling. The research population was employees of Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Branch of Margonda Depok, with the amount of the sample was 69 respondents. The analysis method uses Multiple Linear Regression with a software program, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 25. This study found a positive and significant influence between Work Discipline and Communication on Employee Performance, but not positive and significant between Leadership on Employee Performance. This study concludes that employee performance can be improved through the communication aspect between Leader and Employee. Effective communication will create harmonious work and achievements of the organization's vision and mission. The effect of communication is more dominant than the influence of the other two variables. So that improvement to communication is a priority to improve employee performance.

Keywords:- Leadership, Work Discipline, Communication, and Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

In organizations, technology is a determining factor for success and is also supported by the human resources who work in it. Human resources (HR) are essential assets, and effective management is the key to organizational success (Sinambela, 2016:5). As an asset in the organization, the organization should maintain these assets by the existing capacity to impact organizational goals. Bank Negara Indonesia (BNI) Tbk is one of the BUMN (Stated Owned Enterprises). Like banks in general, BNI also offers banking service facilities such as loans and fund depository. This must be supported by qualified human resources to suit customer needs. Every BNI branch office must have a leader who has a leadership style. Likewise, the level of discipline and work sanctions are applied to each branch office. In work, employees must have communication with each other, both at the same level and subordinates. All of these things have positive and negative influences or impacts on improving employee performance.

This also applies at Bank Negara Indonesia (BNI) Margonda Depok branch. Based on the pre-research conducted by the researcher, there are still problems related to leadership, work discipline, and communication on employee performance. The pre-research with a questionnaire on ten employees, which was carried out, showed that the leadership implemented one-way communication and determined their arrangements. As is known in the banking industry, there will always be an exchange of leaders in each existing branch unit so that the leadership of each leader will always be different in several ways during the performance of employees from the current leadership in the company. This is also supported by research conducted by Siregar (2015) that leadership style has a positive and significant effect on the performance of PT. Bank Danamon Indonesia Pematang Siantar Branch Office. Then, Fazry and Riyanto (2020) stated that leadership has a substantial and positive effect on employee performance at PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero).

Work discipline is a factor that can affect employee performance. The goal of work discipline for the organization is to get an optimal target. However, for employees, the atmosphere of a pleasant work environment encourages employees to do work. Without work discipline in the organization, the expected results will not be achieved because it does not reach the organizational goals and can become an obstacle to implementing the program. This is also supported by research conducted by Syarif and Soleh (2018) that work discipline significantly affects employee productivity at Mayasari Plaza Tasikmalaya. Likewise, with research from Andayaningsih (2016), discipline significantly affects employee performance at PT. Atri Pare-Pare distribution, meaning that with discipline, the performance will be better. Based on the research that has been done, it is known that punitive sanctions can make employees more disciplined at work, but it is not certain that all employees feel it. This can happen because each employee has a different commitment to work, so that it affects employee performance.

Communication is also an obstacle in the organization, such as the lack of interaction between employees when conveying information so that feelings of pressure and stress arise, which ultimately make communication ineffective and efficient. Based on the pre-research that has been done, between colleagues in terms of carrying out work still occurs among employees. Employees who have good communication will be able to obtain and develop the tasks assigned to them because communication itself plays an important role in supporting employee performance in the

company. The results of Nuramalia's research (2016) support that there is an influence of leadership communication on employee performance at the Rural Credit Bank (BPR) South Sumatra. Likewise, the results of Rivai and Suharto's research (2018) that communication partially affects employee performance at PT Bank Capital Indonesia, Menara Kuningan branch.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

Armstrong and Baron (in Fahmi, 2018) explained performance is the aftereffect of work and is firmly identified with the association's essential objectives, consumer loyalty, and commitment to the economy. Then, leadership is talking about process to influence others to promote the achievement of related organizational goals Ivancevich, Konopaske, and Matteson (in Wibowo, 2018). Yuki (in Fahmi, 2018) state "leadership is a process of influencing others to understand and agree about what needs to be done and how to do it, and the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts to accomplish common goals". Leadership is the ability of leaders to influence, motivate, encourage, and promote the activities of all human resources to give their best commitment and contribution to achieving organizational goals.

Work discipline is an attitude of self-awareness to comply with all existing regulations. Meanwhile, according to Keith Davis (in Mangkunegara, 2016), communication is the transfer of information and understanding from one person to another. Then, E. Sikula (in Mangkunegara, 2016) defines that communication as the process of transferring knowledge, experience, and understanding from someone, a place, or something to something, a business, or another person.

A. *The Influence of Leadership on Employee Performance*

In an organization, leadership plays a significant role in achieving organizational goals. Leadership is a process that influences others to facilitate relevant organizational goals (Ivancevich, Konopaske, and Matteson, 2008). Leaders are role models that are respected by their subordinates in an organization. Any changes that will be made must go through the leader first, then coordinated with his subordinates.

In the research conducted by Siregar (2015), leadership style positively and significantly effect on the performance of Danamon Bank Pematang Siantar Branch Office. A study from Fazry and Riyanto (2020) states that leadership has a substantial and positive effect on employee performance at PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero).

Based on those explanation, H₁ is:

H₁: Leadership affects employee performance.

B. *The Influence of Work Discipline on Employee Performance*

Work discipline is essential for employee performance, with high work discipline, employee performance will increase. Hasibuan (2007) states that discipline is a person's awareness and willingness to obey all company regulations

and applicable social norms. In the research conducted by Pangarso and Susanti (2016), work discipline has a huge beneficial outcome on the presentation of the Bureau of Social Service ini Regional Secretariat West Java. Research from Syarif and Soleh (2018) prove work discipline significantly effect on productivity.

Mayasari Plaza Tasikmalaya employees. Likewise, Andayaningsih's (2016) research states that discipline significantly affects employee performance at PT. Atri Pare-Pare distribution, so the higher the field of employees, the better the performance.

Based on those explanation, H₂ is:

H₂: Work discipline affects employee performance.

C. *The Influence of Communication on Employee Performance*

In an organization, effective communication has a critical role because it increases productivity, avoids or resolves conflicts, and develops the potential of each employee. The definition of communication itself is the process of transferring information, understanding, and understanding from someone, a place, or something to something, a home, or another person (Andrew E. Sikula, 1981 in Mangkunegara, 2016). Communication transfers information and understanding from one person to another (Keith Davis, 1985 in Mangkunegara, 2016).

In Nuramalia's research (2016), it is known that there is an influence of leadership communication on employee performance at the Rural Credit Bank (BPR) of South Sumatra. Rivai and Suharto (2018) state that communication partially affects employee performance at PT Bank Capital Indonesia, Menara Kuningan branch. Likewise, Adha and Asriyah (2019) research stated that communication between employees, superiors, and colleagues at BPBD Banten Province was excellent and effective.

Based on those explanation, H₃ is:

H₃: Communication affects employee performance.

D. *The Influence of Leadership, Discipline, and Communication on Employee Performance*

The existence of an organizational role to improve employee performance such as how the leadership of the leader in running the organization, employee compliance in carrying out company regulations, and communication that exists in interactions between employees and between superiors and subordinates.

In the research conducted by Muhammad Roni Suaip and Hesti Widi Astuti (2015), it is known that there is a significant influence between the communication variables on the work discipline of employees at PT. Jamsostek (Persero) Bandar Lampung. Research from Afifah Nasyahta Dila and Thinni Nurul Rochmah (2015) found that if there is an influence between the level of communication effectiveness on employee discipline, the higher the level of communication effectiveness, the higher the employee discipline. Then there is an influence between the point of

the work team on employee discipline, the higher the level of energy of the work team, the higher the employee discipline. Likewise, research from Maudy Rosalina and Lela Nurlaela Wati (2020) found a positive and significant influence of leadership style on employee performance through work discipline.

Based on those explanation, H_4 is:

H_4 : Leadership, work discipline, and communication affect employee performance.

Based on this hypothesis, the conceptual framework of this research can be seen in figure 1

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

III. METHODS

This study used a quantitative method that focuses on the influence between the independent variables, namely Leadership (X_1), Work Discipline (X_2) and Communication (X_3) on the dependent variable, namely Employee Performance (Y) at Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Margonda Depok Branch Office.

A. Definition dan Operationalization Variable Leadership (X_1)

Robbins and Judge, (2011) state that “Leadership is the ability to influence a group towards achieving a vision or set of goals”. The source of that influence may be formal, as provided by managerial levels. The leadership function consists five functions, including (Riinawati, 2019): instruction, consultation, participation, delegation, and control.

a) Work Discipline (X_2)

Sutrisno (in Riadi, 2019) also stated that work discipline is the behavior of a person by the regulations, existing work procedures or discipline is an attitude, behavior, and actions that are following the organization’s rules, both written unwritten. There are 2 (two) types of work discipline (Mangkunegara, 2016): corrective discipline and preventive discipline.

b) Communication (X_3)

Communication transfers information and understanding from one person to another (Keith Davis in Mangkunegara, 2016). The dimensions of communication are divided into four, namely (Robbins in Riinawati, 2019): internal, external, formal, and informal communication.

c) Employee Performance (Y)

Mangkunegara (2016) stated “Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee carrying out his duties following the responsibilities given to him”. According to Rivai (2010), the dimensions of employee work are divided into 6 (six), namely the ability to work, the quality of speed in completing the work, thoroughness or accuracy, loyalty, initiative, and cooperation.

B. Population and Sample

Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Margonda Depok Branch Office, which consisted of 225 employees were the population of this study, and sampling technique used by the author is a probability sampling technique, each member has same opportunity to be a sample (Sugiyono, 2016). In this study, the authors used a proportionate stratified random sampling technique. The proportional stratified random sampling technique in this study amounted to 69 Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Margonda Depok Branch Office employees.

C. Method of Collecting Data

In this study, using primary and secondary data. Primary data was obtained from questionnaires that the research respondents have filled in. The measurement scale used in this study is the Likert Scale sourced from the object of study, which is Bank Negara Indonesia (BNI) Margonda Depok Branch Office.

D. Method of Analysis Data

The data analysis method used is descriptive analysis method and multiple linear regression analysis consisting of validity, reliability, hypothesis testing using SPSS 25.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive analysis describes the variables in the study. In this study, each variable consists of 9 questions which are divided into independent variables, namely Leadership (X_1), Work Discipline (X_2), Communication (X_3), and the dependent variable is Employee Performance (Y). In this study, a series of questions were given to

respondents totaling 69 employees of Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Margonda Depok Branch Office.

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Leadership (X ₁)	69	24	45	36,99	5,129
Work Discipline (X ₂)	69	28	45	38,49	3,76
Communication (X ₃)	69	29	45	37,72	3,869
Employee Performance (Y)	69	29	45	38,2	4,114
Valid N	69	27,5	45	37,83	4,218

Table 1: Statistics Descriptive

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results Version 25 (2021)

Based on Table 1, the statistics above show that Leadership (X₁), Work Discipline (X₂), Communication (X₃) and Employee Performance (Y) with an average value (mean) is 37.83. Leadership (X₁) is the variable with the lowest mean value compared to other variables in this study with 36.99.

B. Validity and Reliability Test

Validity test uses 5% significance, which df = N-2. The value of N in this study is 10, so the value of df = 8 with an r-table value of 0.707. In this study, each r-count are greater than r-table value so that all variables are legit (valid).

The reliability test for all question items in this reserach used Cronbach's alpha formula. The results of the reliability test for the variables as a whole can be seen in table 2.

No	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Limit	Noted
1	Leadership (X ₁)	0.931	0.60	Reliable
2	Work Discipline (X ₂)	0.934	0.60	Reliable
3	Communication (X ₃)	0.944	0.60	Reliable
4	Employee Performance(Y)	0.974	0.60	Reliable

Table 2: Reliability Test Result

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results Version 25 (2021)

Cronbach's Alpha for the Leadership variable (X₁) with a total of 0.931 for all question items. Work Discipline Variable (X₂) with a total of 0.934 question items; Communication variable (X₃) with a total of 0.944 all question items and Employee Performance variable (Y) with a total of 0.974 all question items. In accordance with the description above, the coefficient value of Cronbach's Alpha for all independent variables (X) and dependent (Y) > 0.60, thus all variables in this study are declared reliable.

C. Multiple Linear Regression

In view of test results of the instrument and classic assumption test then multiple linear regression equation was conducted regarding the influence of Leadership (X₁), Work Discipline (X₂) and Communication (X₃) on Employee Performance (Y) can seen in Table 3 below :

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	4.768	3.756		1.270	0.209
Leadership(X ₁)	-0.047	0.071	-0.058	-0.660	0.511
Work Discipline (X ₂)	0.224	0.111	0.205	2.009	0.049
Communication (X ₃)	0.704	0.120	0.662	5.858	0.000

Table 3: Multiple Linier Regression Result

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (Y)

$$Y = 4.768 + (-0.047)X_1 + 0.224X_2 + 0.704X_3$$

X₁ = Leadership
 X₂ = Work Discipline
 X₃ = Communication
 e = Error or error rate

A constant of 4.768 which is a constant value, meaning that if Leadership (X₁), Work Discipline (X₂) and Communication (X₃) are constant, then Employee Performance (Y) is 4.768. The regression coefficient of the Leadership variable (X₁) is -0.047, implying that if the Leadership variable builds, the impact on Employee Performance (Y) will increment by - 0.047 with the supposition that the other autonomous factors are fixed. Work Discipline Coefficient (X₂) of 0.224 implies that if work discipline builds, its impact on Employee Performance (Y) will increase by 0.224 expecting other free factors to be fixed.

Communication variable regression coefficient (X₃) of 0.704 means that if employee performance increases, the effect on employee performance (Y) will increase by 0.704 with the assumption that other independent variables are fixed. With the explanation above, it is concluded that Communication (X₃) has the greatest influence on the Employee Performance of BNI Margonda Depok Branch Office. Leaders are expected to pay attention to communication with their subordinates and also understand how to take policies towards their subordinates. Effective communication, it will create harmonious results and also achieve the target or vision and mission of the organization.

D. R Square

The coefficient of determination test or the R square value is 0.617 or 61.7%. This shows that the percentage effect of the independent variables (Leadership (X₁), Work Discipline (X₂) and Communication (X₃)) on the dependent variable Employee Performance (Y) is 61.7% and the

remaining 38.3% is explained by other variables outside Research Model.

E. Hypothesis Test (t-test)

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
¹ (Constant)	4.768	3.756		1.27	0.209
Leadership (X1)	-0.047	0.071	-0.058	-0.66	0.511
Work Discipline (X2)	0.224	0.111	0.205	2.009	0.049
Communication(X3)	0.704	0.12	0.662	5.858	0

Table 4: Hypothesis Test (t-test)

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results Version 25 (2021)

F. F-test

Simultaneous test (F test) is used to see how the effect of all independent variables (X) together (simultaneously) on the dependent variable (Y). in view table 4, we can infer that F-count (34.922) is greater than F-table with sig. Level under 5% so Ha is accepted. It can be concluded that the variables of Leadership (X₁), Work Discipline (X₂) and Communication (X₃) together have a significant effect on Employee Performance (Y).

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
¹ Regression	710.402	3	236.801	34.922	.000 ^b
Residual	440.758	65	6.781		
Total	1151.159	68			

Table 5: Simultaneous Test Result (F-Test)

a. Dependent Variable: Y

b. Predictors: (Constant), X₃, X₁, X₂

Source: SPSS Data Processing Results Version 25 (2021)

a) The Influence of Leadership (X₁) on Employee Performance (Y)

In light of the Hypothesis test result (t-test), the influence of the leadership variable (X₁) on employee performance (Y) is 0.511 greater than 0.05, and it can be interpreted that the leadership variable (X₁) has no significant effect on employee performance (Y). The partial test (t-test) shows that the t-count is -0.66 and the t-table is 0.235, so the t-arithmetic value is smaller from the t-table, so it tends to be inferred that Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected. Leadership variable (X₁) has no significant effect on employee performance (Y) at Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Margonda Depok Branch Office.

From the results of the correlation analysis between dimensions, it is known that the consideration of the consultation function on cooperation has a fragile relationship, but the reflection of the instruction function on the ability to work has a better relationship even though it is still weak. This illustrates that the attention of a leader to the performance of employee performance is still not good enough, although here, leadership has no significant effect on employee performance. The performance of employees of Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Margonda Depok Branch Office can be improved by improving better relations between superiors and subordinates, both in providing task instructions and also giving support to subordinates in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. Fitrah Yanti M. (2017) also proves that the results show that the leadership style variable has no significant effect on employee performance.

b) The Influence of Work Discipline (X₂) on Employee Performance (Y)

In light of the Hypothesis test result (t-test), has significant value is 0.049, which is smaller than 0.05, So this mean work discipline variable (X₂) significantly effect on employee performance (Y). The partial test (t-test) shows that the t-count is 2009 and the t-table is 0.235, so the t-count esteem is more noteworthy than the t-table, so it tends to be reasoned that Ho is dismissed and Ha is acknowledged. Hence the work discipline variable (X₂) significantly affects Performance employee (Y) of Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Margonda Depok Branch Office.

From the test results of correlation analysis between dimensions, it is known that preventive disciplinary considerations on accuracy or precision have a weak relationship, but corrective disciplinary considerations on the ability to work have a strong relationship. This illustrates if employees still do not obey the organization's work system for accuracy or accuracy at work. Although obedience is the ability to work as duties and responsibilities is very good. Therefore, it is better if the leadership emphasizes or re-appeals policies regarding existing regulations in the workplace and gives appropriate warnings to subordinates who are still unable to carry out the applicable regulations. Muhammad Roni Suaip and Hesti Widi Astuti (2015) also prove that there is a significant influence between the communication variables on the work discipline of employees at PT. Jamsostek (Persero) Bandar Lampung.

c) The Influence of Communication (X₃) on Employee Performance (Y)

In light of the Hypothesis test result (t-test), Has sig. value is 0.00 lowest than 0.05, so it can be inferred that the communication variable (X₃) has a significant effect on employee performance (Y). The partial test (t-test) shows that the t-count is 5.858 and the t-table is 0.235, so the t-count esteem is more prominent than the t-table, so it tends to be presumed that Ho is dismissed and Ha is accepted, so Communication variable (X₃) has an impact. on the

employee performance (Y) of Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Margonda Depok Branch Office.

From the results of the correlation analysis between dimensions, it is known that the consideration of informal communication on loyalty has a very weak relationship, but the consideration of external communication on the ability to work has a strong relationship. This illustrates that communication between fellow employees within the organization is not going well, while communication between employees and customers or people outside the organization is going well. Organizational leaders can improve communication between co-employees in various ways, such as holding an event meeting to establish the intimacy between employees outside of the company's operational working days or hours. Nyimas Nurmalia (2016) also proves that there is an influence of leadership communication on employee performance at the Rural Bank (BPR) South Sumatra.

d) The Influence of Leadership (X_1) Discipline (X_2) Communication (X_3) on Employee Performance (Y)

Based on the simultaneous test (F test) shows an F-count value of 34.922 with a significance value of 5% (0.05), while the F-table value is 2.75 because the F-count value is greater than F-table ($34.922 > 2.75$) and a significant value of $0.00 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It is concluded that the variables of Leadership (X_1), Work Discipline (X_2) and Communication (X_3) together have a significant effect on Employee Performance (Y).

So the results of this study prove hypothesis 4 that Leadership (X_1), Work Discipline (X_2), and Communication (X_3) simultaneously affect Employee Performance (Y). This result is also supported by research by Afifah Nasyahta Dila and Thinni Nurul Rochmah (2015) which shows effects between the level of communication effectiveness on employee discipline.

Based on the explanation of the hypothesis, it can be concluded that only the knowledge sharing variable affects employee performance. Even so, the three variables simultaneously affect employee performance. The facts prove that knowledge sharing can significantly improve performance by exchanging ideas that generate new understanding. Therefore, UPT PT PLN (Persero) Bogor can organize various other programs to increase the intensity of employee exchange of ideas.

V. CONCLUSION

This research could be inferred of discussion, only the leadership variable does not affect the employees of Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Margonda Depok Branch Office performance. Both work discipline and communication variables have significant positive effect on the performance of employees of Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Margonda Depok Branch Office.

However, even so, the three X variables simultaneously impact the performance Bank Negara

Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Margonda Depok Branch Office employees. researchers can continue with different samples and populations. It is expected to use other variables such as job satisfaction, motivation, organizational culture and so on with a larger population so that it can be seen the influence of other variables that can affect employee performance either partially or simultaneously.

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